

***Helicobacter Pylori* Detection via SERS Enhancement Using Synergistic Effects of Gold Nanorods/Nano Mica Platelets/ZnO Quantum Dots**

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ABSTRACT

A highly sensitive and reproducible surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) platform was developed for the noninvasive detection of *Helicobacter pylori* by integrating gold nanorods (AuNRs), nano mica platelets (NMPs), and ZnO quantum dots (QDs) into a ternary hybrid system. AuNRs were uniformly anchored onto the delaminated NMP surface via electrostatic interactions enabled by a cationic interfacial activator. The high surface charge and large specific area of NMPs not only stabilized AuNR growth but also promoted the formation of three-dimensional electromagnetic “hotspots” through particle self-assembly. These AuNRs/NMPs nanohybrids exhibited a significant Raman enhancement effect, achieving a limit of detection (LoD) of 10^{-9} M for adenine with an enhancement factor (EF) of 2.0×10^8 . To further amplify the SERS performance, ZnO QDs were incorporated to introduce additional chemical enhancement via charge transfer. The resulting AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs exhibited a lower LoD of 10^{-10} M, a higher EF of 1.6×10^9 . Remarkably, the same substrate demonstrated excellent sensitivity for *H. pylori* detection, with an LoD of 90 CFU mL⁻¹ and a relative standard deviation of 9.70%. This performance is attributed to the synergistic interplay among localized surface plasmon resonance, semiconductor-mediated charge transfer, and nanoscale self-assembly. The positively charged substrate surface also facilitated efficient physical adsorption of the negatively charged bacterial membrane. Overall, this hybrid SERS platform offers a promising strategy for rapid, label-free, and ultrasensitive detection of *H. pylori*, even in complex biological matrices, and holds great potential for clinical diagnostics and point-of-care applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a gram-negative, microaerophilic, spiral-shaped bacterium that colonizes the human gastric mucosa and is recognized as a major etiological factor in a range of gastrointestinal disorders, including chronic gastritis, duodenal ulcers, gastric adenocarcinoma, and mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma [1]. Since its discovery by Warren and Marshall in 1982 [2], *H. pylori* has remained a global health concern, with an estimated infection rate exceeding 50% worldwide and a considerable risk up to 2% of progression to gastric cancer in untreated individuals [3]. Epidemiological data reveal stark regional disparities in prevalence, ranging from less than 20% in some developed countries to over 80% in regions with poor sanitation and healthcare access [4]. These statistics underscore the urgent need for effective, scalable, and accurate diagnostic methods to manage this prevalent pathogen. Diagnostic approaches for *H. pylori* are typically classified into invasive and noninvasive methods, depending on whether gastric tissue biopsy is involved. Invasive techniques such as histopathology, rapid urease testing, and bacterial culturing offer high specificity but require endoscopy, which is costly, uncomfortable for patients, and dependent on

clinical infrastructure and trained personnel [5]. Noninvasive methods including stool antigen assays, serological antibody tests, and urea breath tests (UBTs) are more accessible, but often suffer from trade-offs in sensitivity, specificity, or safety. In particular, the use of radioactive ^{14}C in UBTs poses potential health risks and limits widespread deployment, while serological assays fail to distinguish active infection from past exposure [6]. Collectively, these limitations highlight the need for a next-generation diagnostic platform that is rapid, label-free, noninvasive, and capable of achieving high sensitivity and specificity across diverse clinical settings.

Surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) has emerged as a powerful molecular fingerprinting technique for ultrasensitive and multiplexed detection, leveraging the intense localized electromagnetic fields (“hotspots”) generated by the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) of metallic nanostructures [7]. Among noble metals, gold nanorods (AuNRs) have gained prominence due to their anisotropic morphology, tunable LSPR into the near-infrared region, and excellent biocompatibility [8]. However, colloidal AuNR systems often suffer from nanoparticle aggregation, poor interparticle distance control, and batch-to-batch variability, which compromise signal reproducibility and restrict real-world biosensing applications. To address these challenges, we introduced a hybrid strategy using delaminated nano mica platelets (NMPs) a two-dimensional (2D) silicate material with high surface area, mechanical rigidity, and strong anionic surface charge to support the self-assembly and stabilization of AuNRs into 3D architectures [9]. This approach enables uniform distribution and alignment of AuNRs, enhancing electromagnetic hotspot density and signal reproducibility. Furthermore, NMPs facilitate strong physisorption of bacterial components via electrostatic and polar interactions, providing an ideal substrate for biosensing. Nevertheless, the signal enhancement in such plasmonic systems remains largely dependent on electromagnetic enhancement mechanism (EM), and further sensitivity gains require incorporation of additional synergistic enhancement modalities.

Despite recent progress, the integration of semiconductor materials into SERS substrates to simultaneously enhance sensitivity and biocompatibility remains underexplored. Composite SERS platforms incorporating semiconductors with high chemical stability, excellent biocompatibility, and large specific surface areas have attracted increasing attention. Such hybrids aim to overcome the inherent limitations of noble-metal-only substrates, particularly through the inclusion of wide-bandgap semiconductors (e.g., ZnO, TiO_2) [10]. Nevertheless, the rational design of these systems is still in its early stages, underscoring the need for a deeper understanding of the underlying enhancement mechanisms. These mechanisms are broadly categorized into EM, governed by LSPR, and chemical enhancement mechanism (CM), primarily driven by charge transfer (CT) processes [11, 12].

Herein, we report the design and application of a novel ternary nanohybrid SERS platform composed of AuNRs, NMPs, and ZnO quantum dots (QDs), specifically tailored for the ultrasensitive and reproducible detection of *H. pylori*. In this system, AuNRs are electrostatically anchored onto the negatively charged NMP surface and further functionalized with ZnO QDs through hydrogen bonding interactions. The resulting AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs exhibit synergistic dual-mode enhancement via LSPR-induced EM and CT-mediated CM, along with 3D hotspot generation from nanoscale self-assembly. This platform achieves an exceptionally low limit of detection ($\text{LoD} = 90 \text{ CFU mL}^{-1}$) for *H. pylori*, and demonstrates high reproducibility, signal uniformity. To our knowledge, this is the first report applying a Au-based SERS nanoplatform for *H. pylori* detection. By bridging materials engineering with plasmonic–semiconductor synergy, this study provides a robust and scalable strategy for real-time, noninvasive bacterial diagnostics and sets the foundation for future point-of-care applications.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

HAuCl_4 (99.9%) and NaBH_4 (98% purity) were purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). AgNO_3 (99.9%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar Co. (USA). Ascorbic acid (99%) was purchased from Acros Organics Co. (USA). H_2SO_4 (95–98%) was purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). Synthetic fluorinated mica (SOMASIF ME-100), composed of Si (26.5 wt%), Mg (15.6 wt%), F (8.8 wt%), Na (4.1 wt%), Al (0.2 wt%), and Fe (0.1 wt%), was purchased from CO-OP Chemical Co.

(Japan). Jeffamine-T403 was purchased from Huntsman Chemical Co. (USA). Bisphenol A epoxy resin BE-188 was purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). HCl (37%) was purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). NaOH was purchased from Macron Fine Chemicals (Avantor Performance Materials, Center Valley, PA, USA). Ethanol (95%) was purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%) was purchased from Showa Chemical Industry Co. (Japan). KOH (>85%) was purchased from Shimakyu Pure Chemicals Co. (Japan). Methanol (99%) was purchased from Echo Chemical Co. (Taiwan). Tetraethoxysilane (98%) was purchased from Acros Organics Co. (USA). Adenine (99.9%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (USA). *Helicobacter pylori* (ATCC 43504) was purchased from Academia Sinica. Blood agar plates (TSA with 5% sheep blood) were purchased from Creative Life Science Co. (Taiwan). Ultrapure water (resistivity = 18.2 M Ω cm at 25 °C) was obtained using a Milli-Q water purification system. All reagents were utilized in their original state without any additional purification or treatment. All glassware was subjected to a thorough cleaning, which involved washing with aqua regia, rinsing with water, and drying.

2.2 Preparation of AuNRs/NMPs

NMPs were prepared in accordance with a previously reported procedure [13]. Polyetheramine (Jeffamine-T403) and epoxy resin (BE-188) were dissolved in ethanol at a 2:1 molar ratio. The solution was stirred for 6 h at 60 °C until a light yellow color was observed, which indicated reaction completion and delaminating agent (T403 AEO) formation. Subsequently, mica (1.0 g, 1 wt%) was expanded at 80 °C for 1 h. A mixture of T403 AEO (4.8 g) and HCl (0.75 g) was ultrasonicated for 30 min (to facilitate the protonation of the amine group and form a quaternary ammonium salt) and added to the expanded mica slurry, and the resulting dispersion was stirred for 5 h to induce mica delamination. The mixture was purified through extraction with dilute ethanolic NaOH, and the solid was redispersed in deionized water to form a 1 wt% NMPs dispersion. Mixtures of NMPs and HAuCl₄ (0.024 M, 0.2 mL) with different weight ratios were supplemented with the gold seed solution (0.1 mL) and CTAB (0.1 M, 10.9 mL) and stirred for 1 h. Subsequently, AgNO₃ (0.01 M, 0.08 mL) and H₂SO₄ (0.5 M, 0.2 mL) were added, and the mixture was dropwise supplemented with ascorbic acid (0.1 M, 0.08 mL). Then, the gold seed solution (0.024 mL) was added, and the dispersion was thoroughly mixed for ~1 min and allowed to stand for ~2 h. The resulting nanohybrid (AuNRs/NMPs) solution was centrifuged at 6,000 rpm for 30 min, and the pellet was washed at least twice with deionized water to remove residual CTAB. The purified solution of AuNRs/NMPs was analyzed using UV-vis spectroscopy, zeta potential measurements, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and SERS.

2.3 Preparation of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs

ZnO QDs were prepared using a sol-gel synthesis method [14]. A methanolic solution of KOH (1 M, 25 mL) solution was slowly added to that of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.1 M, 12.5 mL) at room temperature (25 °C), and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at 1,000 rpm. The presence of ZnO particles was confirmed by the observation of bright yellow fluorescence under UV light. Subsequently, tetraethoxysilane (0.125 mL) was added to regulate particle growth, and deionized water (0.25 mL) was introduced into the resulting gel solution to facilitate a sol-gel reaction on the particle surface. After purification by at least two-fold centrifugation with methanol and deionized water to remove residual reactive molecules, the gel was redissolved in deionized water to form a solution of ZnO QDs. Given the abundance of hydroxyl groups on the silicate nanoclay surface, AuNRs/NMPs with varying weight ratios were physically mixed with ZnO QDs for 15 min to facilitate the stabilization of the two materials through hydrogen bonding and form AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs, which were characterized by TEM, and SERS.

2.4 Culturing of Bacteria and Preparation of SERS Substrate

Prior to bacterial culturing, all glassware was sterilized via autoclaving at an elevated pressure and

temperature (~120 °C, 50 min). The broth was prepared in a 250 mL serum bottle, and *H. pylori* (ATCC 43504) was transferred into the broth (2 mL) using an inoculation ring. Subsequently, the sample was smeared in blood culture medium and cultured in an anaerobic culture tank with microaerobic gas packs at 37 °C for 7 days. The colonies were collected and transferred to a microcentrifuge tube containing 2 mL of the broth using an inoculating loop. The collected bacterial suspension was divided into two 1 mL portions, one of which was used to spread the blood culture medium for the subsequent round of culturing to ensure the continuity and stability of the culture, while the other was subjected to UV-vis analysis and OD600-adjusted to 0.6. Thereafter, the growing colonies were quantified. The bacterial solution was centrifuged at 6,000 rpm for 3 min. The upper layer was removed and washed three times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and then prepared for SERS. Subsequently, solutions of AuNRs/NMPs, and AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs (0.01 mL) were drop-coated onto clean aluminum sheets with dimensions of 10 mm × 10 mm and oven-heated at 80 °C. Analyte solutions were prepared at concentrations of 10⁻⁴–10⁻¹¹ M for adenine (volume = 0.01 mL). The *H. pylori* solution (0.01 mL) was combined with the SERS substrate in a nutrient-free environment and subsequently dried for Raman detection.

2.5 Characterization

UV-vis spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu UV-2450 instrument (Kyoto, Japan). For TEM imaging (JEOL JEM-2100), a 0.01 mL droplet of the SERS substrate suspension was placed on a copper mesh and allowed to dry at 80 °C for 24 h. Confocal micro-Raman spectroscopy (Horiba-LABRAM HR800, 785 nm laser) was used for SERS analysis in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ range (exposure = 10 s, power = 20 mW). Zeta potential analysis was conducted using a Zetasizer Nano ZS90 instrument. Samples for scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6500F) were prepared by drop-coating clean glass surfaces with the desired dispersions followed by oven-drying at 80 °C for 2 h, affixing to a conductive carbon adhesive, and coating with a thin layer of Pt.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Synthesis and Analysis of AuNRs/NMPs

Delaminated layered silicates, such as synthetic fluorinated mica, offer a 2D platform with high surface charge density, mechanical rigidity, and exceptional self-alignment properties ideal for nanoparticle immobilization via cation exchange [15]. In this work, NMPs with lateral dimensions of 300–1000 nm and a thickness of ~1 nm were utilized as a robust scaffold to facilitate the in situ growth and stabilization of AuNRs. As shown in Figure 1a, the negatively charged NMP surface enabled electrostatic adsorption of gold precursors and promoted seed-mediated reduction of AuNRs directly onto the nanosheet surfaces. The reduction process, monitored via UV-vis spectroscopy (Figure 1b), completed within approximately 125 minutes, substantially faster than conventional nanohybrid fabrication approaches. Zeta potential measurements (Figure 1c) confirmed distinct surface potential shifts upon nanoparticle loading, supporting successful AuNR anchoring. To optimize the component ratio, AuNRs/NMPs composites were synthesized at varying weight ratios. At suboptimal NMP concentrations, AuNRs showed pronounced aggregation and irregular morphology, while excessive NMPs led to heterogeneity in particle size and shape due to ionic charge imbalances (Figure 1d, 1e). The optimal dispersion and alignment were achieved at a 1:1 weight ratio (Figure 1e (3)), which yielded the highest SERS signal-to-background (S/B) ratio and signal intensity (Figure 1f). The ultrathin nature of NMPs permits dual-surface adsorption of AuNRs, enabling anisotropic self-assembly and interparticle coupling in the vertical (z-axis) dimension. This hierarchical configuration results in the formation of dense 3D electromagnetic hotspots, significantly amplifying localized field intensity. The optimized substrate demonstrated a LoD for adenine of 10⁻⁹ M and a surface enhancement factor (EF) of 2.0 × 10⁸ (Figure 1g, 1h). These values were derived using the standard EF equation [16, 17]:

$$EF = (I_{\text{SERS}}/C_{\text{SERS}})/(I_{\text{norm}}/C_{\text{norm}}) \quad (1)$$

where C_{norm} and C_{SERS} represent the analyte concentrations under normal and SERS conditions,

respectively, and I_{norm} and I_{SERS} denote the corresponding Raman signal intensities. Collectively, these results demonstrate that AuNRs synthesized and assembled on NMPs under optimized conditions yield uniform, highly active SERS substrates with enhanced signal reproducibility and sensitivity, attributed to well-regulated nanoparticle arrangement and the strong localized field effects at the nanorod tips.

Figure 1. (a) Generation of gold nanorods (AuNRs) on the surface of nano mica platelets (NMPs) using a seed-mediated method. (b) UV-vis spectra of AuNRs/NMPs (1/1, w/w) recorded at different reduction times (n = 10). The spectrum corresponding to the median set was selected for representative plotting. (c) Zeta potentials of HAuCl₄, AuNRs, NMPs, and AuNRs/NMPs (1/1, w/w). (d) UV-vis spectra of AuNRs/NMPs with different component weight ratios (n = 10). (e) Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of AuNRs/NMPs with weight ratios of (1) 5/1, (2) 2/1, (3) 1/1, (4) 1/2, and (5) 1/5 (insets show photographs of corresponding dispersions). (f) Surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) responses of AuNRs/NMPs with different weight ratios to adenine (10⁻⁴ M). Spectra were averaged over 50 randomly selected positions (n = 50), with the median set displayed. (g) SERS responses of AuNRs/NMPs (1/1, w/w) to different adenine concentrations (n = 50). (h) Linear correlation between log(integrated intensity in the range of 704–764 cm⁻¹) and log(adenine concentration).

3.2 Synthesis and Analysis of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs

To further enhance the SERS performance of AuNRs/NMPs, ZnO QDs were incorporated to introduce CT-driven CM alongside EM from plasmonic nanostructures. ZnO, a biocompatible wide-bandgap semiconductor [18], facilitates CM by promoting interfacial electron transfer when the energy levels of the analyte align with the conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB) of the ZnO substrate. This alignment leads to modulation of molecular polarizability and intensification of the Raman signal. ZnO QDs were anchored onto the surface of NMPs through hydrogen bonding with surface silanol (Si–OH) groups (Figure 2a). UV–vis spectroscopy and Tauc plot analysis determined the ZnO QD bandgap to be 3.44 eV (Figure 2b), while energy level mapping revealed favorable alignment between adenine’s highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO)/lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) and ZnO’s CB/VB, confirming the potential for CT-mediated enhancement (Figure 2c). The ternary nanohybrids (AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs) exhibited significantly stronger SERS responses to adenine compared to AuNRs/NMPs alone (Figure 2d). Systematic optimization of component ratios revealed that a AuNR/NMP/ZnO QD weight ratio of 1/1/2 produced the most uniform QD dispersion and maximal SERS response (Figure 2e–f), with a LoD of 10^{-10} M and EF of 1.6×10^9 (Figure 2g–h). The pronounced enhancement arises from the synergistic interplay between EM and CM mechanisms: AuNRs generate highly localized electromagnetic fields, while ZnO QDs enable CT pathways that increase analyte polarizability. Concurrently, the NMP substrate facilitates 3D hotspot formation via AuNR self-assembly, enhancing interparticle coupling and EM field localization. Overall, the integration of ZnO QDs into the AuNRs/NMPs framework significantly amplified SERS performance through complementary EM and CM mechanisms, establishing a robust platform for highly sensitive and reproducible biomolecular detection.

Figure 2. (a) Schematic synthesis of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO quantum dots (QDs). (b) Tauc plot of ZnO QDs. (c) Energy level diagram illustrating charge transfer between ZnO QDs and adenine. (d) SERS responses of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs (1/1/2, w/w) and AuNRs/NMPs (1/1, w/w) to adenine (10^{-4} M). Spectra were averaged over 50 randomly selected positions ($n = 50$), with the median set displayed. (e) TEM images illustrating the distribution patterns of AuNRs, NMPs, and ZnO QDs in AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs with weight ratios of (1) 3/3/1, (2) 2/2/1, (3) 1/1/1, (4) 1/1/2, and (5) 1/1/5. (f) SERS responses of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs with different weight ratios to adenine (10^{-4} M; $n = 50$). (g) SERS responses of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs (1/1/2, w/w) to different adenine concentrations ($n = 50$). (h) Linear fit of the $\log(\text{integrated intensity in the range of } 704\text{--}764 \text{ cm}^{-1})\text{--}\log(\text{adenine concentration})$ plot.

3.3 Interaction of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs with *H. pylori* and SERS Detection

The AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs hybrid substrate enabled sensitive and reproducible detection of *H. pylori* through synergistic EM and CM. As illustrated in Figure 3a, the detection strategy involved physical adsorption of *H. pylori* onto the positively charged nanohybrids, followed by SERS analysis. A strong Raman response was obtained at a bacterial concentration of 1.8×10^7 CFU mL⁻¹ (Figure 3b), with a LoD of 90 CFU mL⁻¹ (Figure 3c) and an excellent linear correlation ($R^2 = 0.9818$; Figure 3d). Signal mapping across 50 random points (relative standard deviation = 9.70%; Figure 3e) and a 400 μm^2 area confirmed outstanding spatial uniformity and reproducibility (Figure 3f). The high sensitivity is attributed to the electrostatic interaction between the negatively charged lipopolysaccharides and phosphoglycerol groups on the *H. pylori* surface and the positively charged CTAB-modified AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs. Figure 3g demonstrates the physical adsorption of *H. pylori* onto the SERS substrate. After a seven-day culture period, the bacteria were washed, centrifuged in PBS, dehydrated with ethanol, and incubated with the AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs substrate for a defined duration. The subsequent formation of a visible precipitate confirmed successful bacterial capture. SEM analysis of the precipitate (Figure 3h) revealed pronounced substrate adhesion to *H. pylori*, observed as distinct white protrusions. Figure 3h (1) shows *H. pylori* cultured without the substrate, serving as a control. Upon increasing contact time, a greater amount of substrate was observed accumulating around the bacterial surface, supporting the hypothesis that *H. pylori* can be effectively captured via physisorption, thereby enabling enhanced SERS detection. Benchmarking against existing SERS platforms (Table 1) highlighted the enhanced performance of our approach in terms of LoD and EF. Unlike UBTs or immunoassay-based fecal detection, which suffer from enzymatic interference or antigen instability, this method provides a rapid, label-free, and noninvasive alternative with high accuracy [19, 20]. Furthermore, its scalable fabrication and compatibility with complex biological matrices underscore its strong potential for clinical diagnostics and point-of-care applications in gastrointestinal pathogen screening.

Figure 3. (a) Flow chart of the SERS-based detection of *Helicobacter pylori* by AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs. (b) SERS response of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs (1/1/2, w/w) to *H. pylori* (1.8×10^7 CFU mL⁻¹). (c) SERS responses of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs (1/1/2, w/w) to different *H. pylori* concentrations. Spectra were averaged over 50 randomly selected positions ($n = 50$), with the median set displayed. (d) Linear fit of the $\log(\text{integrated intensity in the range of } 2840\text{--}3040 \text{ cm}^{-1})\text{--}\log(H. pylori \text{ concentration})$ plot. (e) Raman signal intensities of *H. pylori* (1.8×10^6 CFU mL⁻¹, 2940 cm⁻¹) at 50 randomly selected points on AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs. (f) Distribution of the Raman signal intensity of *H. pylori* (1.8×10^6 CFU mL⁻¹, 2940 cm⁻¹) over a 400 μm² area of AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs. (g) Physical capture of bacteria by AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs and resulting precipitation. (h) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the precipitate in (g). The white wrinkled portion represents the SERS substrate. Image (1) refers to *H. pylori* without any substrate after seven days of culturing, while other images refer to precipitates formed after standing for (2) 10, (3) 20, and (4) 30 min.

Hybrid composition	Analyte molecule	LoD ^{a)} /EF ^{b)}	References
Ag-PCR-M		10 ⁻⁸ M/Not reported	[21]
AuNPs/MoWS ₂		10 ⁻⁹ M/Not reported	[22]
TAuNPs/NMPs	Adenine	10 ⁻⁹ M/5.7 × 10 ⁷	[23]
AuNRs/Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x		10 ⁻⁹ M/1.0 × 10 ⁸	[24]
AuNCs/NMPs		10 ⁻⁹ M/3.6 × 10 ⁸	[13]
AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs		10 ⁻¹⁰ M/1.6 × 10 ⁹	Our work

^{a)}Limit of detection. ^{b)}EF calculated as described in the main text.

Table 1. Performances of different gold nanoparticle-based probes for the SERS detection of adenine.

4 CONCLUSION

This work presents a rationally engineered ternary SERS platform integrating AuNRs, NMPs, and ZnO QDs for the ultrasensitive, selective, and reproducible detection of *H. pylori*. The nanohybrid design leverages the synergistic contributions of multiple enhancement mechanisms: (i) strong EM fields arising from the LSPR of AuNRs, (ii) CM via interfacial CT enabled by the wide-bandgap ZnO QDs, and (iii) a highly ordered 3D hotspot network promoted by the self-assembly of AuNRs on the anionic surfaces of delaminated NMPs. NMPs serve not only as a structural scaffold for uniform AuNR immobilization but also as a physicochemically active interface that enhances particle dispersion, promotes hotspot density, and facilitates the stable incorporation of ZnO QDs through hydrogen bonding. This integrated architecture enables efficient analyte adsorption and amplifies Raman signals through both plasmonic and semiconductor-mediated pathways. The resulting AuNRs/NMPs/ZnO QDs exhibit exceptional analytical performance, achieving a LoD of 10⁻¹⁰ M for adenine and 90 CFU mL⁻¹ for *H. pylori*, with high signal reproducibility (RSD = 9.70%). Taken together, these findings demonstrate the potential of this multi-component SERS platform as a powerful tool for next-generation, noninvasive bacterial diagnostics. The integration of plasmonic, silicate, and semiconducting nanomaterials within a single, scalable framework opens new avenues for high-performance biosensing in clinical and point-of-care environments.

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